

FORMS OF MANIFESTATION OF THE VOLUNTEER MOVEMENT IN THE ROSTOV REGION DURING THE GREAT PATRIOTIC WAR*

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Abstract

An indicator of the national and domestic character of the Great Patriotic War was, among other things, the mass volunteer movement shown by Soviet citizens literally immediately after its beginning. In its essence, scale, social and ethnic composition, forms, military and political significance, it was a truly unique phenomenon of domestic, and indeed of the entire world history.

The volunteer movement during the war included citizens who voluntarily expressed a desire to go to fight with the enemy and wrote a corresponding application to the military enlistment offices with a request to be sent to the front, two main categories: those who, by their age and state of health, were liable for military service and were subject to conscription after the announcement of mobilization and those who, by virtue of their, too young or elderly, illness, or having had an official exemption from conscription due to his important professional activity (the so-called "armor"), they were not subject to conscription. The volunteer movement in the Rostov region was very active and massive.

The first volunteer formations in the region were fighter battalions. In July 1941, 77 fighter battalions with a total strength of 16 thousand people were formed. On July 5, 1944, a special resolution of the Rostov Regional Committee of the CPSU (b) on the organization of units of the people's militia is issued. The Rostov Rifle Regiment of the People's Militia was formed. In the Don villages, literally from the first days of the war, a mass volunteer movement of Cossacks arose. Among the volunteer Cossacks there were young men who had not reached the draft age, and elderly men whose age was already much higher than the draft age. During the temporary occupation of the Rostov region by the Nazi invaders, the Don partisans and underground fighters fought courageously behind enemy lines. Members of partisan detachments operating throughout the region and based in the most suitable secret places of residence, and underground groups located directly in the settlements of the region, should also be attributed to the participants of the volunteer movement.

The mass volunteer movement that unfolded in the Rostov region, in terms of its content and forms of implementation, had both common, characteristic for all regions of the country, and special characteristics. Its features were the large participation in it of volunteers of various age and social categories, from cities, villages and villages of all districts of the region, the formation of volunteers from the Cossacks of the Don Cossack cavalry volunteer division, a very significant number of partisan detachments.

Keywords: volunteers, volunteer movement, people's militia, units, partisans, the Great Patriotic War.

The volunteer movement during the war included citizens who voluntarily expressed a desire to go to fight the enemy and wrote a corresponding application to the military enlistment offices during the war, Soviet citizens submitted more than 20 million applications to military, Soviet and party organizations with a request to enroll them in the army [1, p.26]. But due to various objective with a request to be sent to the front, two main categories: those who, by their age and state of health, were liable for military service and were subject to conscription after the announcement of mobilization and those who, by virtue of their non-conscription, too young or old, illness, or having an official exemption from conscription due to his important professional activity (the so-called "armor"), They were not subject to conscription. At one time, a study by A.M. Sinitsyn noted that and subjective circumstances (unsuitable age, poor health, official "reservation"), a significant part of these applications were not satisfied. During the

Great Patriotic War, the official number of volunteers in the USSR enrolled in various volunteer militia formations amounted to more than four million people [2, p.183].¹

Various formations, units and subunits of the so-called people's militia began to form from volunteers. These were volunteer military and paramilitary formations of various types, purposes, numbers and forms of organization (communist regiments and battalions, combined military detachments of party, Komsomol, Soviet assets, militia regiments, as well as numerous fighter battalions subordinate to the NKVD to protect important rear facilities, maintain order, fight enemy landings and saboteurs). Militia military units, in the form of divisions and regiments, totaling more than two million people [2, p.183], were sent directly to the front line only at the most critical moments of the fighting, mainly during the initial period of the war as military support to regular units of the Red Army.

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Tens of thousands of residents of the Rostov region expressed a desire to volunteer for a deadly fight against the enemy. The first volunteer formations in the region were fighter battalions. Their education began immediately after the release of the decree of the Bureau of the Rostov Regional Committee of the CPSU (b) "On measures to combat paratroopers and enemy saboteurs on the territory of the Rostov region." In accordance with this resolution, fighter battalions of 100-200 people were formed in all districts of the region, who were not subject to priority conscription, from the most "proven, brave, selfless Communists, Komsomol members, Soviet activists capable of wielding weapons, without interrupting their constant work" [3, pp.24-25]. A lot of work was carried out in this direction very quickly, as a result of which, by July 17, 1941, 77 fighter battalions with a total of 16 thousand people were formed in the region. Several assistance groups were created for each battalion, the total number of which was 2,118 units. In total, there were 23,500 people in the fighter battalions and their assistance groups [4, p.48].

Taking into account the fact that many thousands of residents of the region, including those who were not subject to conscription for mobilization, declared their desire to voluntarily go to the front, on July 5, 1944, a special resolution of the Rostov Regional Committee of the CPSU (b) on the organization of militia units was issued. Already in July 1941, hundreds, battalions, and regiments were formed from the militia in almost all cities and districts of the region. On July 10, 1941, the order of the commander of the Rostov garrison, Major General A. A. Grechkin, was issued on the formation of the Rostov Infantry Regiment of the people's Militia. Its commander was appointed deputy director of the car assembly plant, captain of the reserve M. A. Varfolomeev. In just a month after the release of this resolution, more than 60 thousand applications from volunteers were submitted in the city of Rostov, about 1.4 thousand in the city of Shakhty, over 1.6 thousand in the city of Kamensk, over 7.2 thousand in the city of Taganrog, more than 2.3 thousand in the Zverevsky district, about 1.7 thousand in Belokalitvinsky, more than 1.3 thousand in Egorlyk [5, p.174]. On October 15, 1941, a new Rostov militia regiment began to be formed, which on November 10 joined the Rostov Infantry Regiment of the People's Militia.

In the Don villages, literally from the first days of the war, a mass volunteer movement of Cossacks arose. On July 15, a joint resolution was adopted by the Bureau of the Rostov Regional Committee of the CPSU (b) and the Rostov Regional Executive Committee "On the creation of the Don Cossack Division in the Rostov region." It was to be staffed by volunteer Cossack hundreds of 4 platoon personnel formed in various districts of the region, each numbering 135 people, from persons "... regardless of their age / not subject to conscription/, but able to carry weapons" [3, p.62]. The volunteer Cossack division that was being formed in the Rostov region was named the "Don Volunteer Cossack Cavalry Division". On January 21, 1942, on the basis of a directive from the General Staff of the Red Army, the

Don Volunteer Cossack Cavalry Division was officially renamed the 116th Don Cossack Cavalry Division. Colonel P. Ya. Strepukhov was appointed commander of the division. On January 26, 1942, the division became part of the active army. Volunteers often joined this division with their families. For example, the Cossack I. A. Khomutov, already at an advanced age, joined the volunteer division together with his sons, 14-year-old Alexander and 16-year-old Andrei. Cossack Vyshkvartsev joined one of the Cossack regiments of the people's militia together with his wife and son. Cossack Zubenko arrived at the assembly point with his wife, son and two daughters. Together with their sons, the Cossacks Sklyarov, Chernoyarov, Fedorov and many others joined the militia [6, pp.17-18]. Among the Volunteer Cossacks there were also very young men who had not reached military age, in particular, the youngest of them, Alexander Khomutov, was only 14 years old, and very elderly men of unsuitable age, for example, the oldest Volunteer Cossack Nikolai Erokhin was already 67 years old [7, p.179]. In the spring of 1942, the 116th Don Cossack Volunteer Cavalry Division became part of the 17th Cossack Cavalry Corps. It is noteworthy that in one of the reports of the political department of the 116th Don Cavalry Division to the political department of the North Caucasian Military District on the state of the division it was noted: "The absolute majority of Cossacks are volunteers. More than 80% of the rank and file are Cossacks over the age of 40 (that is, very old age - V.T.), participants in the civil war... There are squadrons manned by Cossacks of the same district" [8, p.84]. Later, this division was renamed the 12th Guards Don Cossack Cavalry Division and became part of the famous 5th Guards Don Cossack Cavalry Corps.

The volunteer movement on the Don continued in the following war years. At the same time, it was expressed in the spirit of the main forms: the desire of citizens to go to the front on their own and in the so-called Komsomol mobilizations. So, in 1942, the Komsomol mobilization of girls for service in the air defense forces was announced in the country in order to send the men released there to the front. About 200 thousand girls on Komsomol mobilizations became fighters of the air defense forces, communications units, etc. [9, p.204]. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that Komsomol mobilizations were not officially mandatory and Komsomol members could either voluntarily respond to them and volunteer for the army, or ignore them. In the second case, to the maximum, they could only declare penalties on the Komsomol line. That is, Komsomol mobilizations, in their essence, were also one of the forms of the volunteer movement.

In the Rostov region, according to this Komsomol mobilization, quite a lot of Komsomol girls volunteered for service in two air defense regiments in the emerging air defense units. Their female fighters bravely fought the enemy. And the feat accomplished by the anti-aircraft gunners of the 3rd battery of the 734th Air Defense Regiment went down in the history of the war as a true example of heroism and courage. At the same time, for a number of objective reasons, he remained unknown for many years, and only recently, thanks to

the research of search engines, he received coverage in historical works and publications of the media.

During the temporary occupation of the Rostov region by the Nazi invaders, Don partisans and underground fighters courageously fought behind enemy lines. Members of partisan detachments and underground groups should also be classified as members of the volunteer movement. After all, they joined these formations exclusively voluntarily. In the summer and autumn of 1941, 83 partisan detachments with a total number of about 3,395 people were formed in the region, even before its first occupation, in a very short time [10, p.162].

The peculiarities of the natural, mainly steppe, landscape of the Rostov region, the practical absence of significant forests and other natural shelters for the deployment of partisan detachments, as well as the proximity of the front, had the most direct effect on the tactics of their actions. A significant part of the detachments were forced to operate from the frontline of the non-occupied part of the region. In May 1942, there were 67 partisan detachments in the region, with a total number of 2,324 people [3,p.362]. The partisan struggle was especially active in the summer and autumn of 1942, after the enemy occupied almost the entire territory of the Rostov region, with the exception of only two northern Vyoshensky and Verkhnedonsky districts. At this very difficult time for the country, the Don partisans and underground workers, constantly risking their own lives, selflessly fought the enemy. Two partisan detachments ("Brave - 1" and "Brave - 2") were particularly successful in the Neklinovsky district of the region, three ("Azovsky", "Alexandrovsky -1st" and "Alexandrovsky-2nd") in the Azov district. In difficult conditions, in the Don steppes, partisans of the "Angry Don" detachments of the Zavetinsky district, "Don Cossack" of the Migulinsky district, named after Kirov, named after the Rostov Regional Committee of the CPSU (b), "Steppe Eagle" of the Oryol district, fighters of the Taganrog detachment operating in this rural area, as well as partisan detachments of Semikarakorsky, Kiev, Kolushkinsky, Litvinovsky and other districts of the Rostov region.

The Don underground workers fought bravely and selflessly against the enemy. In addition to the Stalin detachment, underground groups "Tramwayman", "Avenger", "Oath", Lenzavodskaya, G. F. Jolika and others operated in the city of Rostov. The activities of Taganrog underground workers became a bright and tragic page of the national struggle against the enemy.

During the period of enemy occupation in the territory of the Rostov region, a total of 163 partisan detachments and underground groups operated in different periods of time, numbering about 4,990 people in their ranks [7, p.200].

Thus, literally from the very beginning of the Great Patriotic War, a mass volunteer movement unfolded in the Rostov region. In terms of its content and forms of implementation, it had both common, characteristic for all regions of the country, and special characteristics. The general content elements include the exclusively voluntary nature of its participants, significant mass participation, participation of representatives

of various age and social categories of citizens, and the special ones include the large participation of Don Cossacks, often even parents with their children and entire families, a significant number of volunteers from villages and villages of all districts of the region. The general forms of implementation of the volunteer movement include the creation of paramilitary and military units common to other regions of the country, such as fighter detachments and assistance groups, militia units, partisan detachments, and special ones – the formation of the Don Cossack cavalry volunteer division from volunteers, the preliminary organization, despite the lack of necessary landscape and geographical conditions for their successful activities, of a very significant number of partisan detachments, some of which operated not directly on the territory of the region, but from the location of the frontline units of the Red Army, the presence of the only urban partisan detachment in the country named after Stalin, stationed and operated directly in the city of Rostov-on-Don.

Volunteer units, formations and detachments formed in the Rostov region, in particular, the Rostov Rifle Regiment of the People's Militia, the Don Volunteer Cossack Cavalry Division, later renamed the 116th Don Cossack Cavalry Division, and then became the 12th Guards Don Cossack Cavalry Division, despite the serious losses they suffered in the bloody and very difficult heavy fighting of the initial period of the war, they were included as regular units in the Red Army.

Actively operating in the territory of the region, in very difficult unfavorable landscape and geographical conditions of the steppe strip, quite numerous partisan detachments, the total number of which for the entire period 1941-1943 was 163 units, inflicted very significant losses on the enemy in manpower and equipment.

The volunteer movement in the Rostov region played an important role during the war, especially at its very difficult initial stage. The Don volunteers steadfastly and courageously fought the enemy and made their considerable contribution to the Victory.

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